

Investigation of Insect Pests of the Moth bean (*Vigna aconitifolia*) in Taranagar Tehsil of Churu (Rajasthan) during the Kharif Season – 2022

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Abstract

Due to its nutritional content, moth beans are an important pulse crop in India. Its grain is rich in vitamins, minerals, protein and carbohydrates. The moth bean crop is raised in India throughout the kharif and summer seasons. Numerous species of insect pests attack the moth bean crop, greatly harming the crop and yield for the farmer. These pests lower the yield and quality of moth beans. This project included an experiment to assess insect pests on moth bean crops during the kharif season. This experiment was conducted at Taranagar on a farm.

In Rajasthan, Taranagar is a tehsil of Churu district. This experiment used a 10 m ×10 m plot size with a 20 cm row to row and 15 cm plant to plant spacing to produce the RMO- 40 variety of moth bean. *Empoasca motti*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Holotrichia consanguinea*, *Phyllotreta cruciferae*, *Ophiomyia phaseoli*, *Nezara viridula*, *Aphis crassivora*, *Caliothrips indicus*, *Amsecta moorei*, and *Odontotermes obesus* were among these insect pests. These insect pests began to affect crops as seedlings and persisted through agricultural maturity.

Keywords

Jassid, White Fly, Insect Pests, Flea Beetle, White Grub, Moth Bean.

Introduction

In various linguistic areas of India, moth bean (*Vigna aconitifolia*) is known by a number of regional names, including Kheri, Bhioni, Matki, Math, Madike, and Kunkuma. It is a crucial product in semi-arid and arid areas of Rajasthan. Approximately 1.11 million hectares of moth bean are grown in India, with an annual output of 0.31 million tonnes and a productivity of 277 kg/hectare (Anonymous,2018).On the other hand Gujarat produces 0.15 million tonnes yearly over a 0.32 million hectare area (Anonymous, 2016).

It is primarily grown in Rajasthan, Haryana, Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Uttar Pradesh in India. About 75–80% of the nation's output comes from the state of Rajasthan. It is the only pulse grain grown in the Churu, Bikaner, Barmer, Jaipur, Jalore, Jhunjhunu, Nagaur, Jodhpur, Sikar, and Pali districts during Kharif in Rajasthan's arid region. The moth bean is a multipurpose product because it can be used as pasture, feed,fodder, green manure, and a source of sustenance. Vegetables from green pods are delectable. Being a pulse, it is an affordable supply of vegetable protein to make up for a lack of certain nutrients.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to investigation of insect pests of the Moth bean (*Vigna aconitifolia*) in Taranagar Tehsil of Churu (Rajasthan) during the Kharif Season – 2022.

Review of Literature

Despandey and Rao (1954), as well as Pant and Tulsiani (1963), noted that pulses make up to 26% of the country's total protein and about 11% of its total calorie consumption. 'Dal' (bean stew) and 'bhujia' (crispy snack) are two common ways that moth bean seeds are used in India. They are also used to make moth bean fritters, papad, mangori, rabri, and vada (Senthilkumar and Ngudi, 2020). While fried, split moth beans are easily ingested, both cooked and sprouted seeds are a common breakfast option (Medhe et al., 2019). According to Panicker and Hamdule (2021) and Verma et al. (2021), moth bean also possesses anti-hypertensive, anti-oxidant, anti-cancerous, anti-bacterial, diuretic, and hypocholesteromic effects.

The moth bean kernel has a moisture content of 10.30%, a protein content of 25.66%, a fat content of 2.78%, a mineral content of 0.41%, a fiber content of 3.90%, and a carbohydrate content of 61.76%. Comparatively speaking, moth bean has more protein. Leucine and lysine, two amino acids, are also found in abundance in it. But a variety of pests, such as insects, rats, and animals, seriously damage this crucial crop. Pests are thought to be responsible for up to 40% of the yearly crop output losses worldwide. The insect pests that attack the moth bean plant can be classified into groups based on how they appear in the field, according to the phenology of the plant. They are hence foliage feeders, stem feeders, pod feeders, and storage pests. Numerous foliage-feeding insects from the genera lepidoptera and coleoptera eat the foliage of moth bean and many other related legumes. Most of these insects are particularly polyphagous and will consume both legumes and other types of food. Several insect pests, including the white grub (*Holotrichia consanguinea*), termite (*Odontotermes obesus*), jassid (*Empoasca motti*), whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*), galerucid beetle (*Madursia obscurella*), stem fly (*Ophiomyia phaseoli*), red hairy caterpillar (*Amsacta moorei*), flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae*), thrips (*Caliothrips indicus*) and pod borer (*Catechrysops cnejus*); which have been documented to seriously threaten its cultivation by causing moderate to severe damage from germination to maturity (Bindra and Singh, 1969; Puttaswami et al., 1977; Parihar, 1979; Satyavir, 1980; and Pareek et al., 1983).

Satyavir et al. (1984) revealed that jassids and whiteflies also serve as a vector for the yellow mosaic virus in addition to producing direct damage by desapping. According to Singh and Singh's (1978) research, the use of proper intercropping is gaining ground in overall pest management strategies due to its physical and biological effects on the succession and population growth of insect pests. To keep up with the population's constant growth, the nation must generate ever-increasing amounts of goods. The impact of the Green Revolution has led to India becoming self-sufficient in the production of food grains today. It has transitioned from being a food-importing nation to one that exports food. The extensive input consumption has led to a number of issues with agricultural sustainability. Pollution is affecting the air, water, and soil. Due to the evolution of human requirements, the agricultural sector now requires significant adjustment.

Methodology

The field study of insect pests of the moth bean crop was carried out from July to October in 2022 kharif season. The experiment was conducted on a small farm in the Taranagar tehsil of Churu district. According to Hussain (2015), this site is situated in Rajasthan's hyper- and partial-irrigated agro-climatic zone. On the moth bean crop, insect pest infestation was seen on the RMO-40 type produced on a 10mx10m plot with a 20cm row to row and 15cm plant to plant spacing. Throughout the trial, the crop under investigation was both exposed to natural infection and free of insecticides. Pest bug surveillance on the crop began at the seedling stage and continued through crop harvest. Insect pests were collected for this experiment using hand nets, light traps, and aspirators. Pests were transferred into killing bottles for the purpose of identification. With the aid of an entomological pin and setting board, the nuisance insect corpses were mounted and stored. The collected insect pests are then identified using a taxonomic key and the recognised pests are temporarily housed in an insect collection box.

Result and Discussion

According to study of insect pests of moth bean during kharif season – 2022 recorded that many insect species were infested on moth bean crop. These insect pest were jassid (*Empoasca motti*), whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*), White grub (*Holotrichia consanguinea*), Flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae*), Stem fly (*Ophiomyia phaseoli*), green bug (*Nezara viridula*), Aphid (*Aphis crassivora*), Termite (*Odontotermes obesus*), Red hairy caterpillar (*Amsacta moorei*) and Thrips (*Caliothrips indicus*). These insect pests cause a lot of harm to plants by sucking sap and eating leaves.

According to Anand et al. (2020), nine insect species, including *Aphis crassivora*, *Empoasca motti*, *Bemisia tabaci*, *Mylabris pustulata*, *Helicoverpa armigera*, *Lampides*

boeticus, *Spoladea recurvalis*, and *Diaphania indica*, are infesting the mung bean crop.

Anand et al. (2023) reported that the whitefly and Jassid are major insect pests of mungbean crop. Several insect pests, such as the white grub (*Holotrichia consanguinea*), termite (*Odontotermes obesus*), jassid (*Empoasca motti*), whitefly (*Bemisia tabaci*), galerucid beetle (*Madursia obscurella*), thrips (*Caliothrips indicus*) stem fly (*Ophiomyia phaseoli*), red hairy caterpillar (*Amsacta moorei*), flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae*) and pod borer (*Catechrysops cnejus*) have been reported to damage the crop at different stages of plant growth and to cause moderate to severe damage from germination to maturity, posing a serious threat to its cultivation (Bindra and Singh, 1969; Puttaswami et al., 1977; Parihar, 1979; Satyavir, 1980 and Pareek et al., 1983). *Bemisia tabaci*(Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a widespread cotton whitefly that is a significant polyphagous pest of green gram (Panduranga et al. 2011, Mishra and Mukherjee 2015), black gram (Taggar and Gill 2012), and moth bean (Singh et al. 2010) in India.

Fig.1. White Fly

Fig.2. Jassid

Fig.3. Green Bug

Fig.4. Flea Beetle

Fig.5. White grub

Fig.6. Termite

Fig.7. Red hairy caterpillar

Fig.8. Stem fly

Fig.9. Aphid

Table 1: Insect pests of moth bean, *Vigna aconitifolia* (Jacq.) Marechal

Sr. N.	Common name	Scientific name	Order	Family	Genus	Species
1	Aphid	<i>Aphis craccivora</i>	Hemiptera	Aphididae	Aphis	A. craccivora
2	Jassid	<i>Amposca Motti</i>	Hemiptera	Cicadellide	Amposca	A. motti
3	Whitefly	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>	Hemiptera	Aleyrodidae	Bemisia	B. tabaci
4	Thrips	<i>Caliothrips indicus</i>	Thysanoptera	Thripidae	Caliothrips	C. indicus
5	Flea beetle	<i>Phyllotreta cruciferae</i>	Coleoptera	Chrysomelidae	Phyllotreta	P. cruciferae
6	Stem fly	<i>Ophiomyia phaseoli</i>	Diptera	Agromyzidae	Ophiomyia	O. phaseoli
7	White grub	<i>Holotrichia consanguinea</i>	Coleoptera	Scarabaeidae	Holotrichia	H. consanguinea
8	Termite	<i>Odontotermes obesus</i>	Blattodea	Termitidae	Odontotermes	O. obesus
9	Green bug	<i>Nezara viridula</i>	Hemiptera	Pentatomidae	Nezara	N. viridula
10	Red hairy caterpillar	<i>Amsacta moorei</i>	Lepidoptera	Arctiidae	Amsacta	moorei

Whitefly: Whiteflies are a major pest of moth beans and carry the Yellow Mosaic Virus. The occurrence of whiteflies often peaks around the second week of September. The nymphs and adults specifically suck the cell sap from the surface of the leaves.

Jassids: From the crop's vegetative stage through harvest, this pest is present. The cell sap is consumed by both adults and nymphs. The adult is a little insect that consumes leaves. The leaves become black, curl, and eventually dry out before falling to the ground in cases of severe infection.

White Grub: The white grub is a large beetle that causes severe damage to a number of crops, including the moth bean. Beetles emerge from the soil and feed on a variety of host foliage trees after it has rained. The beetles pair together and lay their eggs before returning to the soils. There is only one generation of grubs per year. The grub eats the roots between months July to October.

Stem fly: One of the most dangerous pests of the moth bean crop is the stem fly. At the seedling stage, stem fly maggot infestations take place. Early symptoms of the disease include thickening or stem cracking at or just above ground level in the affected plants. The plant eventually dries out, becoming yellow and stunted. In order to eat, the maggots bore into the stem. Plants with infestations experience yellowing of the leaves, and adults pierce the foliage, causing yellowing of the punctured areas.

Flea beetle: The appearance of flea beetle damage is distinctive. They consume food by first chewing a tiny hole in a leaf, moving a short distance, then chewing another hole, and so on. The outcome resembles several "shot holes" in the leaf. Flea beetles lay their eggs on or near plants in the surrounding soil. The little larvae feed on the plant's roots, barely harming edible crops.

Green bug: A green bug, feeds by puncturing and sucking the growing seeds. Due to this, partially formed seeds shrivel and young seeds abort. Seeds that have fully grown display coloring around the depressed puncture point. Bug management is crucial because the quality of moth bean seed determines its value, particularly its capacity to sprout uniformly and with a high germination rate.

Aphid: The bean aphid is a soft-bodied, dark-green to dark-gray insect that is frequently observed in large clusters on fragile young growth. It is a member of the Aphididae family and one of the most damaging insect pests. It feeds on plant sap using a piercing sucking mouthpart. Bean aphid is a well-known pest that farmers hate because of its prodigious reproductive ability.

Termite: Termites are multivorous pests that harm numerous crops economically. Both vegetative and reproductive stages of moth bean crops damaged by termite (*Odontotermes obesus*). Termites tunnel into the stem and roots the bore causes the plants to quickly dry up.

Red hairy caterpillar: When they are in the neonate stage, these hairy caterpillars scrape the underside of the leaf. Later, the scraped-off leaf patches resemble thin

paper. Larvae at full development eat all of the vegetation, flowers, and growth points. Long reddish brown hairs cover the entire body of the hairy caterpillar larva.

Thrips: The direct feeding injury produced by thrips larvae and adults results in economic damage. The sap from the buds and blooms is sucked by nymphs and adults, causing their drop.

Conclusion With a higher protein content than other crops, pulses are one of the world's most significant food crops. India is the global leader in both pulse production and consumption. In India, moth bean is one of the important pulse crops. Moth bean is heavily infected with insect pests By sucking sap and devouring plant leaves. These insect pests seriously destroy crops. Insect Pests cause damage to crops at every stage of development, from seed germination to crop maturity. In this study, the highest presence of insect pests of Hemiptera order was observed among the insect pests attacking the moth bean crop. These insect pests are belong to the families viz. Aphididae, Cicadellide, Aleyrodidae and Pentatomidae. As a result, these insect pests are responsible for significant economic losses for farmers.

Suggestions for the future Study India is an agricultural country. Most of the population of this country depends on agriculture for their livelihood. Moth bean is an important pulse crop grown in dry areas that is infected by various types of insect pests from seed germination to maturity. This infestation of insect pests affects all parts of the plant, such as the root, stem, leaf, etc. Due to this, the farmers are not able to get full benefit from their produce. This study will be helpful in providing information about the moth bean insect pests and the damage caused by them.

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